

THE IMPORTANCE OF SOCIAL DESIGN IN FIGHTING RACISM IN THE UK

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a social design case study aimed at improving the relationships within multicultural communities in the UK. The REWIND project was initiated to tackle racism among young people in the UK through specifically designed workshops. An example of the workshop conducted with young people is presented. Through the analysis of the REWIND project we can observe how the multi-disciplinary team can provide powerful tools and methodology to improve multi-cultural social interaction.

Keywords: social design, community education, branding, racism.

INTRODUCTION

For long design has been narrowly seen as a way to improve profit. It then developed from product sales to mirroring or even eliciting consumers' dreams. However, design has now found a new wider scope where it engages with social issues and tries to find solutions. As design clearly triggers emotions in the public by fulfilling dreams, so it can also have a wider emotional impact and change the public's behavior to solve social problems such as crime, poverty or environmental issues.

In this paper, the REWIND project is discussed as this is a case study of applied social design, which addresses the issue of racism in the UK. This project shows how social design can address current social issues and is able to provide solutions, making use of design tools and a multi-disciplinary approach, change the public's emotions related to false beliefs or stereotypes.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

It is easy to connect design with style and sales profits as we have been bombarded by publicity, with the aim of convincing the public into buying a product or service. Arguing in favor of a wider approach to design, Whiteley (1993) cites the words of design writer Jeremy Myerson who has criticized the fact that '*design is fast becoming a weapon of exclusivity, of segmentation – the means by which many desirable goods and services are put out of reach of large sections of the community*'. On this wider view, design has an important role into people's lives and is not confined to sales. It can influence behavior and ideas through the various media and adverts as well as be used by people to help themselves describe who they are and what they like through the choices of brands and what they consume or use (Papanek 1968, Whiteley 1989, Ollins 2000, Klein 1999).

As design can influence consumers' behavior and fulfill desire, it can be argued that design emotionally links to people. It is undeniable that its influence can have an impact within society (Whiteley 1989) as it helps individuals identify themselves with something that might be intangible such as the experience in a hotel or the fantasy of having a relaxing holiday abroad (Lo, 2011).

The ability to connect to people's emotion is a very powerful tool for designers and it should be carefully used. As for Papanek (1984), the idea that *design should be meaningful* is crucial. The author argues that since design shapes our environment, society and mankind itself requires social responsibility.

According to Papanek (1984), design should bring real change to society and that as creative individuals designers should use their skills to solve social problems. Furthermore, design 'must' be responsive to the true needs of the people, innovative, highly creative and a cross-disciplinary tool. Research orientated design could yield better results in identifying and addressing those needs.

Likewise, Browne (2009) sees design as an important tool to improve society and argues that *design thinking* can be a tool to find solutions also by the use of a multi-disciplinary team. A multi-disciplinary team can bring together a wide variety of perspectives to solve a problem. The solution does not need to come from a specialist in the field where the problem is addressed. In fact, by using a multi-disciplinary team tailored to solve a specific problem brings higher chance of finding a successful solution because the team will have a richer insight of how a problem can be solved. Bringing together the tools and communication skills of designers with the knowledge of social issues by social enterprises will enrich perspectives, methodologies and tools to be employed in tackling social issues. This co-operation can bring more success to social enterprises' projects for the benefit of society, while fulfilling individuals who work for it.

Nowadays, social design is widely recognised. Various governmental bodies and charities have been encouraging the participation of local communities within social movements and engaging with environmental issues, for instance. The Design Council in the UK has brought together a number of individuals and creatives to collaborate to find solutions for social issues, through design challenges. For instance, 'Dott 07' was a design challenge where the council sponsored a year of community based projects, competitions, exhibitions, conferences, symposia, and festivals throughout the north-east England to explore questions such as '*Can design help in the fight against crime?*', '*Are our food production systems ripe for a redesign?*' or '*How can design make schools more sustainable?*'

Another of the major social challenges that our fast changing society in the UK has to face is racism. Such a delicate and meaningful topic as racism can take advantage from design and exploit this new important role of designers.

Living in a society that has a large number of different cultures and backgrounds brings various challenges. Most of all, the challenge is to bring together different communities by guaranteeing their rights, while respecting their identity. Misunderstanding of each cultural identity cannot always be addressed solely by laws and policies. People's beliefs and education play a huge role into shaping their behavior and approach to different cultures. As seen above, a new approach to design can become a powerful tool to improve society and thus also to address issues concerning racism. The Rewind Project has been developed to address this issue and is supported by the Home Office, National Youth agency, Runnymede Trust and endorsed by the Institute for 'Race' relations.

THE REWIND PROJECT

The Rewind Project does not seem to be rooted into a specific pedagogical or psychological perspective, as their inspirational speaker Paul Obinna, who heavily influences this project, does not seem to have grounded his work into theory. However, its methodology, centred around *concept de-construction* and by explaining racism as entrenched beliefs through socially constructed myths, seems to borrow assumptions from social constructivism. A social constructivist as Said (1981) clearly describes and explains how social concepts, used in identifying or stigmatising different social groups, are interpreted differently and are the result of social conventions and historical processes. These theoretical assumptions are the ground for Rewind's methodology which uses historical reconstruction and the de-construction of racist concepts to highlight their fallacy, with the aim of changing false beliefs and myths.

By exposing these myths their work takes a more in-depth approach to tackling racism than the '*multi-cultural*' approach which emphasizes respect for differences only and does not challenge deep seated racist beliefs.

Figure 1. REWIND's concept deconstruction process method.

The methodology is applied by using factual information gathered from a varied multi-disciplinary team made of geneticists, biologists, anthropologists, historians, psychologists, researchers, charities as well as anti-racists campaigners and general media articles.

To help develop this project, the REWIND team needed to create branded material to convey the message effectively and engage participants.

The design of the material to be used within these workshops and lectures were crucial to create a link between users and speakers. Because they were dealing with young adults and teenagers, the material needed to be designed in an engaging way as well as challenge their ways of thinking through activities.

Figure 2. REWIND workbook. All rights reserved to REWIND 2006

The material for this project included the design of:

- DVD to be shown at lectures and workshops
- worksheets for the lecturers and teachers
- workbook for the teenagers and students
- website to expand the project awareness and to facilitate the communication with other organizations that might be interested in this project

THE WORKSHOP PROCESS

The structure of the workshop follows four main sections which focus on the importance of addressing:

- 1) The issue of racism;
- 2) Rejection of immigrants as part of society;
- 3) Racism which emerged through the legacy of slavery;
- 4) The concept of *race*.

The educator breaks down each section even further by:

- Giving an introduction about the topic being dealt with in the section they are working on and present the aims that want to be reached by the end of this work module;
- Ask questions to get the teenagers to start thinking about the topic to be further discussed later in the workshop;
- Show a DVD video that is relevant to this section;
- Reintroduce questions and add new ones for further reflection of the group;
- Get the teenagers and adults to run group activities.

Figure 5. REWIND workshop. Presenting news headlines for group discussion, image taken from REWIND DVD. All rights reserved to REWIND 2006

Figure 6. REWIND workshop. Group discussion challenging concepts, image taken from REWIND DVD. All rights reserved to REWIND 2006

This process helps not only reinforcing the topic through different media formats, but also adds dynamism to the workshop and engages more the group of young adults to be interested in the topic.

In the first section of the workshop, REWIND's educators give a small introduction to the teenagers about racism by challenging them to think if racism is an issue in the UK today. They will ask the pupils if they have experienced or seen some kind of racism within their neighborhood, school or sport environment and challenge them to think if racism is an issue within their lives.

Within the second section of the workshop, the REWIND team questions the idea of rejection of immigrants as part of the society they live in. By analysing the background history of the British territory and the various invasions it suffered throughout many years, they challenge the pupils into thinking if the idea of '*send them back to where they came from*' is logical or has any positive impact. The educators challenge the idea of the concept of '*Britishness*' by reminding the workshop's attendees if they took into consideration how many different populations invaded the island before the UK was defined as being a country. They argue that all British descendants have some level of connection to a foreigner population and therefore the statement '*go back from where you came from*' is a racist statement and it should not apply to anyone in the UK. They also highlight that much of the cultural richness of the British society comes from its long term multi-cultural elements and that alone should be cherished, not condemned.

In the third section of the programme, the group analyses the historical influence of the slave trade, the profit made by Britain in those days and the legacy that remained within the society. In this module they highlight how many ports such as Liverpool and Bristol have been built thanks to the profit made from the slave industry.

Within the fourth and final section of the workshop, the educators challenge the concept of '*race*', defined as differences in the genetic pool between one ethnic group and another. This is a clear example of concept de-construction. With the support of scientific evidence, borrowed from anthropology and genetics, the educators show that humans are made up of more than thirty thousand genes. Therefore, classifying ethnic groups by emphasising the importance of a very few genes, only because they are more apparent, as they define us physically, is misleading.

The outcome of the project has been very positive within the schools and communities where it has been applied and received a number of positive feedback, both from institutions as well as individuals that attended the workshop. (See feedback appendix 1).

By offering educational background and challenging myths that have been well accepted within society, the project manages not only to educate young adults, but also to influence their behaviours in recognising racism as a problem to act upon it. Many of the students signed up to help the organisation as volunteers to the project, showing that a well-designed project creates enthusiasm and is not only an effective tool for the project.

CONCLUSION

Social design is a powerful approach, which allows us to address social issues and find solutions in a very creative and effective way. As we have seen, Browne's vision is applied within the REWIND project: a multi-disciplinary approach, which has made wide use of different media and which shaped people's behaviour by changing their emotions linked to false beliefs and stereotypes.

Through questionnaires, relevant feedback could be provided to collect qualitative data with the aim to measure the efficacy of the method and improve it. Testimonials which have been provided as feedback for the project are not a fully suitable tool for the above purpose.

This case study is an attempt towards social inclusion. However more work can be done in the future beginning with in-depth analysis of these preliminary results. Furthermore, work should be done to promote social change and change people's behavior to improve society as a whole. This can be achieved through the use of social design and a multi-disciplinary team co-operation. Addressing key issues that need tackling and improving collaboration between various professionals, it is crucial to educate society and encourage better behaviours in a more effective way, now and for the future generations.

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APPENDIX 1

PROJECT FEEDBACK FROM ATTENDEES.

Their project delivery and impact have been supported by various individuals and institutions.

Head teacher of Hateley Heath primary school
"Your approach was fresh and exciting and you actually involved all our children in your presentation. I was particularly impressed with your approaches to tackling cultural issues The science perspective certainly "fired up" the older children who (later) engaged in quite a detailed debate about genetics! I have no difficulty in recommending this work to other schools" (Year 5 and 6 pupils)

Pupils from Hateley Heath School
"I would recommend Rewind to other Primary Schools to help them understand more about racism and to help decrease racism towards other pupils. The videos we used were filled with useful information packed in and it was brilliant to watch. I have learnt a lot of things and I enjoyed working with Denise and Sahida".

Pupils from Hateley Heath School
"I really enjoyed working with Rewind. Denise, Sahida and Dave made things very clear about not to be racist. I learnt a lot from Rewind and found out that only 6 genes control your skin colour. I recommend other schools invite Rewind to help people to understand that racism is not a nice thing. In fact, it is horrible and disgraceful. The videos and photographs that Rewind showed were amazing and very informative. The Rewind group are very enthusiastic and appreciate them coming and helping us".

George Salter High School, Y. Norton, Teacher of Geography
"REWIND sessions were suitable for all pupils as it catered for the needs of differing learning styles, such as the use of video's, group work, movement around the room..... It tackled racism well by letting pupils make decisions on particular aspects of racism..... I would not hesitate to recommend other schools or

groups to undertake REWIND training" (Year 7 pupils).

University of Birmingham, Youth community play and youth program student
"undoubtedly this is the best module I have attended so far. The tutors were 'spot on' with their approach" (comments from student)

Willingsworth High School, Year 8
"People who discriminate are just insulting themselves because there is only one race"

George Salter High School, Year 8 pupil
"it showed that white, black and Asian people are all related"

Great Bridge Primary School, Year 5 pupils
"there is only one race, the human race" "we learnt about that thing in our skin that makes us different colours (melanin)" "we learnt that we can all be related"

Arun Kundnani, from the Institute of Race Relations, makes a remarkable declaration of how effective this programme has been: *"In taking this approach, REWIND is distinctive. It does not touch on standard discussions of cultural awareness, or celebrating diversity. Unfashionably, yet effectively, REWIND does not give you a better understanding of different religions or expose you to the usual pantheon of multi-cultural role models and artifacts. Its aims simply to undo racism by going back to its origins (hence 'REWIND') and raising awareness of that history, rather than the history of any specific culture.for people who experience racist abuse themselves; REWIND appears to offer a kind of strategy for dealing with racist situations..."*